

SOHAM

**An International Multidisciplinary Peer
Reviewed Research Journal**

ISSN: 2350-0697

Impact Factor 5.810

Volume-38 Issue-6 Oct. - Dec. - 2023

**Editor - In - Chief
Dr. Dilkhush U. Patel**

EDITORIAL BOARD

Editor – In – Chief

Dr. Dilkhush U. Patel
[MA, PhD]

Principal
V.N.S. B. Ltd. Arts and Commerce College
Vadnagar, Gujarat

MEMBERS OF ADVISORY BOARD

Dr Niranjan Patel
Dean,
S.P. University, V.V.Nagar, Anand

Dr. Dilip Patel
Former Registrar
Hemchandracharya North Gujarat University, Patan

Dr. J. K. Patel
Principal
Shri V. R. Patel College Of Commerce, Mehsana

Dr. Sanjay Shah
Principal
Arts, Commerce & Science College, Pilvai

Dr. Dinesh N. Patel
Assi. Professor, Dept. of Accountancy
V.N.S. Bank Ltd. Arts and Commerce College, Vadnagar, Gujarat

Members of Review Board

Sr. No.	Name	Subject	Email
1.	Dr. M.F.Patel Principi C.C.Mahila Arts & C.N. Commerce Commerce College, Visnagar	English	ccmcnc@yahoo.com
2.	Mr. Jaydeepsingh G. Rao, PhD Assistant Professor, IITE Gandhinagar.	English	Jaydeep.rao05@gmail.com
3.	Dr. Hirendra R. Pandya Assistant Professor Vadnagar Arts & Commerce College	Gujarati	Hirendra.pandya@gmail.com
4.	Dr.Arti Patel Shrimati P.R.PatelArts College,Palasar	Gujarati	Soham2217@gmail.com
5.	Dr. A. S. Gami Associate Professor A/C College, Chanasma	Sanskrit	Soham2217@gmail.com
6.	Dr.. K. H. Patel Associate Professor Vadnagar Arts & Commerce College	Commerce	Kamupatel1966@gmail.com
7.	Dr. J. P. Patel Associate Professor Department of Biology, V.P. & R.P.T.P Science College Sardar Patel University	Science	Soham2217@gmail.com
8.	Dr. K. G. Patel principal, Gujarat College,Ahmsdabad	History	researchguru125@gmail.com
9.	Dr.Nita J. Joshi Associate Professor Smt. C. R. Gardi Arts College, Munpur	Hindi, Proof- Reader	nitajoshi94@gmail.com
10	Dr. M.A.Saiyed Associate Professor Smt. C. R. Gardi Arts College, Munpur	Sociology	Soham2217@gmail.com

Content of the Table

Sr.No.	Title of the Paper/Article	Author	P. No
1	Does any effect of The New Education Policy on Mental Health?	Dr. Bhavna Gajera,	1
2	Is National Education Policy to Strengthen Language?	Dr. Chandrika Savsani	3
3	National Education Policy And Value Building	Dr. Minaxi Patel	5
4	Multilingualism and the power of language in reference with National Educational Policy - 2020	Dr. Sunanda Patel	7
5	Political view of national education policy 2020	Prof. Sunita Makwana	10
6	The National Education Policy (NEP) of 2020 and India's Economic Growth	Dr. Manoharsinh Rajjada	12
7	Impact of New Education Policy on Indian Society	Dr. Nirmala Aghera	14
8	Indian knowledge system & New Education Policy 2020	Dr. Girajashankar Joshi	16
9	India's New Education Policy 2020- Key Changes and Implications	Dr. C. K. Mehta	19
10	A Comprehensive Study of Cyber Law and Cyber Crimes	Dr. Mayuri P. Dave	23
11	Decoding the New Education Policy 2023 in India	Dr. P M Undhad	28
12	Education in the Indian Context	Dr. Poonam P. Joshi	33
13	International Financial Reporting System	Dr. Vanali K. Vadoliya	38
14	A Comparative Profitability study of selected online selling companies in our country	Prof. Yoginiben Chaudhari	42
15	National Education Policy 2020: A catalyst for rebuilding India	Dr. Punit Teraiya	52
16	Artificial Intelligence in Psychology	Dr. Ranjitsinh Parmar	55
17	Artificial Intelligence in Accounting	Dr. Sharadchandra Narendrabhai Solanki	57
18	George Orwell's 'Shooting an Elephant' - A postcolonial study	Bakulsinh Balsinh Bhateriya	60
19	Delineation of Higher Education Policy: A Perspective	Dr. Dipikaben K. Rohit	64

20	An Investigation on Impact of Digital Payments Adoption on Payment Infrastructures in Indian Economy	RICHA MAKWANA	67
21	National Education Policy-2020: Role of Commerce Teachers	Shailesh B. Yadav	75
22	"AN EMPIRICAL STUDY TO MEASURE FACTORS AFFECTING PURCHASE INTENTION IN LUXURY BRANDS IN TERMS OF RATIONAL AND EMOTIONAL IMPACT IN AHMEDABAD CITY"	Gianchandani Damini Hareshkumar DR. D.N. Patel	80
23	Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni's Mistress of Spices: A Study	Dr. Minaben Jesangbhai Chaudhari	89
24	A Proactive Mechanism of Robotic Process Automation in Accounting and Finance	Pankaj Parmeshwar Sharma	93
25	Over - Valuation of IPO: A Red Alert for Investors	Vaibhav Parmanand Gallani	100

A Proactive Mechanism of Robotic Process Automation in Accounting and Finance

Pankaj Parmeshwar Sharma

Assistant Professor (GES-II)

Shri K. K. Shastri Government Commerce College, Ahmedabad.

Vaibhav Parmanand Gallani

Assistant Professor (GES-II)

Shri K. K. Shastri Government Commerce College, Ahmedabad.

Abstract

In the modern era of automation the Robotic Process Automation is a significant automation technology that plays vital role in the overall solutions. RPA can significantly enhance the productivity and efficiency of businesses. The adoption of RPA technology is growing globally. Therefor this study is directed to identify the present and potential application of RPA technology in the areas of finance and accounting. To meet the objective of study the data will be collected from the secondary sources. The available reports, articles, and research papers on application of RPA technology in the areas of finance and accounting are studied. This study identified that the adoption of RPA can be made to automate invoice processing, expense reporting, payroll management, exception flagging, risk management, inventory management, credit scoring, audit support, financial reporting and forecasting. This study concludes that the robotic process automation in finance and accounting enhances accuracy, reduces operational costs, accelerates processes, and allows finance and accounting professionals to concentrate on high-value tasks, analysis, strategic thinking, and decision-making. This study will be useful to businesses in incorporating the RPA technology in the areas of finance and accounting to enhance productivity and efficiency.

Keywords: Robotic Process Automation, Finance, Accounting, Business, Technology.

Introduction

RPA stands for Robotic Process Automation. It's a technology that uses software robots (bots) to automate repetitive tasks, allowing businesses to streamline processes and increase efficiency. In other words it's about using software "robots" capable of following specific rules and action sequences, you can automate processes that typically require human workers to perform tedious intervention. Robotic accounting is a form of robotic process automation or RPA, which is used in the accounting field. It uses software bots, in order to eliminate the need for human input in accounting processes. Software bots are computer programs designed to perform certain actions, in this case, accounting tasks. This is in a nutshell the description of robotic accounting software. It can be utilized using a rule-based approach or implementing AI algorithms to automate accounting tasks performed by bots. Robotic accounting centralizes data from different bookkeeping systems and helps the financial department optimize accounting operations, for instance, managing payslips or processing invoices. Take invoices as an example. With robotic accounting, the software bots take the invoice and check it, extract information, and transfer the data to an accounting system, without human input. Additionally, RPA in accounting minimizes the risk of fraudulent transactions occurring, as it helps identify document fraud.

Diagram 1: Robotic Process Automation

RPA bots mimic human actions in carrying out a task within a process. These software applications can execute repetitive tasks quickly, accurately, and consistently. For accountants, RPA provides a unique opportunity to optimize their accounting processes. Do not think of automation as "set it and forget it" technology for modern accountant. Instead, the accounting and finance experts need to continuously analyse the results that are achieved while considering how to improve even further.

Literature Review

Authors	Year	Insights	conclusions
Dariusz & drzejka	2019	RPA can be used in accounting and finance for tasks such as procure-to-pay, invoice processing, and payroll automation, leading to increased efficiency and reduced cycle time.	RPA has the potential to automate accounting processes. Accountants' roles will shift towards business advisory and leading RPA transformation.
Kokina et al.	2021	RPA is changing the work of accountants in accounting and finance tasks, and accountants play roles as identifiers, explainers, trainers, sustainers, and analyzers in RPA implementations.	Accountants play important roles in RPA implementations. Accountants need to acquire new technical skills.
Qiu & Xiao	2020	The paper discussed the application of RPA in cost management optimization of a financial shared service center, providing insights for RPA application in accounting and finance.	Current cross-system data cannot be automatically collected. Cost accounting is not timely.
Lacurezeanu et al.	2020	This paper discussed the RPA in auditing and accounting.	RPA can improve performance and credibility in accounting and auditing services while reducing costs and streamlining activities.
Ortiz & Costa	2020	This paper assessed the efficiency gain of using RPA in a finance process and presents a bridge between information systems and RPA.	Efficiency gain when automating processes with RPA. Bridge between information systems and RPA presented.
Cooper et al.	2021	The paper examined how the adoption and use of RPA is affecting the perceived work experience in Big 4 accounting firms.	Both firm leaders and lower-level employees agree that RPA has a positive influence on the profession. Firm leaders believe RPA will improve work satisfaction, but lower-level employees report no such improvements.
Zhang et al.	2022	The paper explored the implementation of RPA in the accounting function and identifies themes related to its adoption.	Five themes related to RPA adoption in accounting - workforce, IT governance, privacy and security, system sustainability, and measurement of success. Key takeaways for effective RPA adoption in accounting.
Edghiem et al.	2022	This chapter explored the application of robotic process automation (RPA) in the accounting domain, specifically in	RPA can be applied in the accounting domain. Lebanese economic crisis affected compliance with IPSASs.

		the context of the Lebanese economic crisis.	
Li	2021	This paper analyzed the development, application, and impact of financial robots (RPA) in enterprises.	Financial robots are an opportunity for transforming Financial work systems. The paper proposes suggestions for Introducing Financial robots.
Guin et al.	2021	The paper addressed the use of RPA in a financial institution and proposes methods to minimize the number of robots required for transaction processing.	Four heuristics used to compute an upper bound on the number of required software robots. Two heuristics outperform others in finding optimal solutions.
Bakarich & O'Brien	2021	This paper assessed the use of artificial intelligence technologies in the public accounting profession	RPA and ML are not extensively used in public accounting. AI will significantly impact accountants' responsibilities in 5 years
Cabrita et al.	2021	The paper discussed the implementation of Robotic Process Automation (RPA) in accounting and finance.	Proposal of a framework for successful RPA implementation in financial institutions, but does not specifically mention its application in accounting and finance.
Kokina et al.	2019	This paper studied the accountant as digital innovator and their roles and competencies in the age of automation.	RPA is changing the work of accountants in accounting and finance tasks, and accountants play roles as identifiers, explainers, trainers, sustainers, and analyzers in RPA implementations. Accountants play important roles in RPA implementations. Accountants need to acquire new technical skills.
Lauren et al.	2019	This paper assessed the robotic process automation in public accounting	The study found that RPA software, also known as bots, is being used in all areas of accounting firms, with the most traction in tax services, followed by advisory and assurance services. Bots have increased Efficiency and quality in accounting firms. Bot implementation is not reducing headcount.
Huang & Vasarhelyi	2019	This paper studied the framework for applying robotic process automation (RPA) in auditing.	RPA has been widely adopted in the accounting industry to automate repetitive tasks, but its application in auditing has been limited. RPA framework proposed for auditing tasks. Feasibility of RPA demonstrated in confirmation process.

Otaru et al.	2020	The paper provided a critical review of existing empirical studies on RPA adoption and its impact on financial decisions.	RPA adoption leads to improved productivity and significant returns on investment. More empirical studies are needed to definitively settle the RPA debate.
Benkalai et al.	2020	RPA is particularly useful for managing large amounts of data in financial institutions, where millions of transactions are processed daily with short processing times.	Two solution methods for the RPA problem are compared, using the lower bound reduces running times.
Eulerich et al.	2021	The paper discusses the development of a framework to assist auditors in deciding which tasks to automate using robotic process automation (RPA) in accounting.	Developed and validated a Three-step evaluation framework. Provides insights on effectiveness and adoption of emerging technologies in audit.
Pokharkar	2019	RPA can be used in accounting and finance to automate repetitive tasks, reduce errors, improve efficiency, and ensure compliance with regulations.	RPA can help banks reduce costs and improve service quality. Automation can enable banks to operate 24/7.

Future Forward

The future of accounting and finance with RPA looks promising. RPA technology can intelligently handle business processes, financial processes, and diverse data, providing technical support for the integration of financial and management accounting (Jiang, 2023). RPA financial robots have characteristics of precision, reliability, high efficiency, low consumption, and rapid response, which can greatly influence traditional financial accounting (Dong, 2022). RPA robots can free financial personnel from boring and tedious work, allowing enterprises to use more resources for financial analysis and scientific decision-making, enhancing the added value of work (Ma and Wang, 2023). RPA and robotic process automation technologies are becoming compulsory for business operations in organizations across the globe, bringing immediate value to core business processes in various sectors (Madakam et al., 2019). In the context of the Lebanese economic crisis, RPA can help overcome the challenges faced by the accounting system and business entities, ensuring compliance with accounting standards (Edghiem et al., 2022).

Need for Adoption of RPA in Accounting and Finance

The adoption of Robotic Process Automation (RPA) in accounting and finance yields a myriad of benefits. Firstly, RPA significantly enhances efficiency by automating repetitive and time-consuming tasks such as data entry, reconciliations, and transaction processing. This not only accelerates processes but also minimizes the risk of human errors, thereby improving the accuracy of financial records. The cost savings are substantial as organizations can streamline operations, reducing both time and resource expenditures. Moreover, RPA ensures stringent compliance with regulatory requirements and internal policies, mitigating the risk of non-compliance and associated penalties. By automating routine tasks, accounting and finance professionals can redirect their efforts towards more strategic activities, fostering better decision-making and adding greater value to the organization. The transparency provided by RPA's audit trail not only facilitates internal audits but also builds trust with external stakeholders. Additionally, the scalability of RPA allows for efficient management of varying workloads, ensuring adaptability to changing business demands.

Application of RPA in Accounting and Finance

In accounting, RPA can be a game-changer. It automates routine, rule-based tasks, reducing errors and freeing up time for more strategic activities. This also has several applications in the field of finance,

optimizing processes and improving efficiency. Common applications in Finance and Accounting include:

Invoice Processing: Bots can extract data from invoices, validate information, and update accounting systems, speeding up the entire invoicing cycle.

Transaction Processing: Bots can handle routine financial transactions, such as payments, refunds, and account updates, reducing the time and potential errors associated with manual processing.

Data Entry: Automation handles mundane data entry tasks, minimizing the risk of manual errors associated with traditional data input.

Exception Flagging: The business can lose money or find itself on unsteady footing if staff members don't notice problems until it is too late. Because RPA is heavily rule-based, it is exceptionally well-suited for detecting when violations of specific business parameters occur. The robot can then route the exception to the appropriate authority for resolution.

Reconciliation: This process involves time-consuming data entry, extraction, and cross-checking. RPA can reconcile accounts by comparing large volumes of data, identifying discrepancies, and flagging them for review by accounting professionals. Automation reconciles accounts efficiently and improving the accuracy of financial records.

Expense Management: Companies accumulate expenses from different business activities. Expense reporting is crucial for efficient bookkeeping and finance management. However, this process is tedious and costly when performed manually. Bots assist in processing employee expenses, ensuring compliance with company policies and reducing the time spent on reimbursement tasks.

Payroll Management: Managing employee payroll involves several time-consuming tasks, such as data extraction and entry, timesheet validation, scheduling payments, and calculating pay-outs and deductibles. To avoid payment delays and inaccuracies, use RPA to automate payroll management. Robust RPA bots can extract data from different sources and calculate deductions and bonuses with accuracy, complying with tax requirements.

Financial Reporting and Forecasting: Corporates monitor their financial performance by tracking and reporting profits and losses accurately and consistently. However there are many challenges of updating P&L reports manually. Automation can compile and generate financial reports, pulling data from various sources and presenting it in a standardized format. They can also improve financial planning and forecasting by leveraging historical data and relevant information in documents. Using RPA to automate this business process will enhance transparency and accuracy.

Risk Management: RPA assists in monitoring and managing risk by automating the collection and analysis of data for risk assessments. This enables quicker response to potential issues. When potential risk violations arise because of specific transactions or changes in the company's financial vitals, the system can produce an alert for attention.

Regulatory Compliance: Automation ensures that financial processes adhere to regulatory requirements by consistently applying rules and quickly adapting to changes in regulations.

Inventory Management: Inventory accounting is all about capturing stock levels in financial records, from profit & loss reports to balance sheets. This business process requires accuracy, making it ideal for automation. RPA bots can streamline inventory management by monitoring, forecasting, and alerting inventory levels and placing stock orders. The application of RPA in e-commerce and retail stores will improve lead times, reduce stock-outs, and optimize storage costs.

Credit Scoring: Bots can analyze creditworthiness by processing and evaluating large sets of financial data, helping in making informed decisions about lending or credit approval.

Financial Planning and Analysis: RPA streamlines budgeting, forecasting, and variance analysis, allowing finance professionals to focus on strategic planning and decision-making.

Audit Support: Bots assist auditors by quickly retrieving and organizing financial data, facilitating audits and ensuring compliance with auditing standards. RPA provides a transparent and traceable audit trail, helping auditors track changes and ensuring compliance with regulatory requirements.

Conclusion

The main objective of this study is to identify the present and potential application areas of Robotic process automation in accounting and finance. The RPA has advanced significantly since its original introduction to till date in for business. For corporates it emerges as a transformative force, contributing to operational excellence, risk management, and overall business success in the realms of accounting and finance.

This study identified that the adoption of RPA can be made to automate invoice processing, expense reporting, payroll management, exception flagging, risk management, inventory management, credit scoring, audit support, financial reporting and forecasting. It is also found that accounting automation using RPA offers several benefits, including reduced costs and losses and improved productivity and regulatory compliance. This study concludes that the robotic process automation in finance and accounting enhances accuracy, reduces operational costs, accelerates processes, and allows finance and accounting professionals to concentrate on high-value tasks, analysis, strategic thinking, and decision-making. This study will be useful to businesses in incorporating the RPA technology in the areas of finance and accounting to enhance productivity and efficiency.

References

- Arkadiusz, Januszewski., Jaroslaw, Kujawski., Natalia, Buchalska-Sugajska. (2021). Benefits of and Obstacles to RPA Implementation in Accounting Firms. *Procedia Computer Science*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.PROCS.2021.09.245>
- Asmita, Pramod, Pokharkar. (2019). Robotic Process Automation: Concept, Benefits, Challenges in Banking Industry. <https://doi.org/10.33771/IIBM.V4I1-2.143>
- BriAuna, Keys., Yibo, Zhang. (2020). Introducing RPA in an Undergraduate AIS Course: Three RPA Exercises on Process Automations in Accounting. *Journal of Emerging Technologies in Accounting*, <https://doi.org/10.2308/JETA-2020-033>
- Chanyuan, Zhang., H., Issa., Andrea, M., Rozario., Jonas, Sveistrup, Soegaard. (2022). Robotic Process Automation (RPA) Implementation Case Studies in Accounting: A Beginning to End Perspective. *Accounting Horizons*, <https://doi.org/10.2308/horizons-2021-084>
- Dariusz, J. (2019). Robotic Process Automation and Its Impact on Accounting. *Zeszyty Teoretyczne Rachunkowości*, <https://doi.org/10.5604/01.3001.0013.6061>
- Dong, Y. (2022). Influence of RPA Financial Robot on Financial Accounting and Its Countermeasures. In: Macintyre, J., Zhao, J., Ma, X. (eds) The 2021 International Conference on Machine Learning and Big Data Analytics for IoT Security and Privacy. SPIoT 2021. Lecture Notes on Data Engineering and Communications Technologies, vol 97. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-89508-2_5
- Edghiem, F., Hariri, N., & Alkhalifah, E. S. (2022). The Application of Robotic Process Automation (RPA) in Accounting: The Perspective of the Lebanese Economic Crisis. In M. Ali (Ed.), *Future Role of Sustainable Innovative Technologies in Crisis Management* (pp. 113-124). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-9815-3.ch009>
- Frag, Edghiem., Noha, Hariri., Eman, Alkhalifah. (2022). The Application of Robotic Process Automation (RPA) in Accounting. *Advances in electronic government, digital divide, and regional development book series*, <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-9815-3.ch009>
- Feiqi, Huang., Miklos, A., Vasarhelyi. (2019). Applying robotic process automation (RPA) in auditing: A framework. *International Journal of Accounting Information Systems*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ACCINF.2019.100433>
- Felipe, C., Magrin, Ortiz, Carlos, Costa. (2020). RPA in Finance: supporting portfolio management: Applying a software robot in a portfolio optimization problem. <https://doi.org/10.23919/CISTI49556.2020.9141155>
- Huang, F., & Vasarhelyi, M. A. (2019). Applying robotic process automation (RPA) in auditing: A framework. *International Journal of Accounting Information Systems*, 35, 100433.
- Imène, Benkalai., Sara, Séguin., Hugo, Tremblay., Geoffrey, Glangine. (2020). Computing a lower bound for the solution of a Robotic Process Automation (RPA) problem using network flows. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CODIT49905.2020.9263933>
- Januszewski, A., Kujawski, J., & Buchalska-Sugajska, N. (2021). Benefits of and obstacles to RPA implementation in accounting firms. *Procedia Computer Science*, 192, 4672-4680.
- Jiang, Y. (2023). Analysis of the Integration of Financial Accounting and Management Accounting under RPA Technology. *Academic Journal of Business & Management*. Vol. 5, Issue 13: 40-46. <https://doi.org/10.25236/AJBM.2023.051307>.
- Julia, K, Ruth, G., Shay, B., Donna, S. (2021). Accountant as Digital Innovator: Roles and Competencies in the Age of Automation. *Accounting Horizons*, <https://doi.org/10.2308/HORIZONS-19-145>
- Julia, Kokina., Ruth, Gilleran., Shay, Blanchette., Donna, Stoddard. (2019). Accountant as Digital Innovator: Roles and Competencies in the Age of Automation. *Social Science Research Network*, <https://doi.org/10.2139/SSRN.3449720>
- Kathleen, M., Bakarich., Patrick, E., O'Brien. (2021). The Robots are Coming ... But Aren't Here Yet: The Use of Artificial Intelligence Technologies in the Public Accounting Profession. *Journal of Emerging Technologies in Accounting*, <https://doi.org/10.2308/JETA-19-11-20-47>

- Lauren, A., Cooper., D., Kip, Holderness., Trevor, L., Sorensen., David, A., Wood. (2021). Perceptions of Robotic Process Automation in Big 4 Public Accounting Firms: Do Firm Leaders and Lower-Level Employees Agree?. *Journal of Emerging Technologies in Accounting*, <https://doi.org/10.2308/JETA-2020-085>
- Lauren, A., Cooper., D., Kip, Holderness., Trevor, L., Sorensen., David, A., Wood. (2019). Robotic Process Automation in Public Accounting. *Social Science Research Network*, <https://doi.org/10.2139/SSRN.3193222>
- Lauren, A., Cooper., D., Kip, Holderness., Trevor, L., Sorensen., David, A., Wood. (2020). Perceptions of Robotic Process Automation in Big 4 Public Accounting Firms: Do Firm Leaders and Lower-Level Employees Agree?. *Social Science Research Network*, <https://doi.org/10.2139/SSRN.3445005>
- Lauren, A., Cooper., D., Kip, Holderness., Trevor, L., Sorensen., David, A., Wood. (2019). Robotic Process Automation in Public Accounting. *Accounting Horizons*, <https://doi.org/10.2308/ACCH-52466>
- Ma, J. and Wang, R. (2023). "RPA Financial Robot Boosts the Digital and Intelligent Transformation of Enterprise Finance", *International Conference on Distributed Computing and Electrical Circuits and Electronics (ICDCECE)*, Ballar, India, 2023, pp. 1-7, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDCECE57866.2023.10151192>.
- Madakam, S., Holmukhe, R. M., & Jaiswal, D. K. (2019). The future digital work force: robotic process automation (RPA). *JISTEM-Journal of Information Systems and Technology Management*, 16.
- Marc, Eulerich., Justin, Pawlowski., Nathan, J., Waddoups., David, A., Wood. (2021). A Framework for Using Robotic Process Automation for Audit Tasks. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, <https://doi.org/10.1111/1911-3846.12723>
- Marc, Eulerich., Justin, Pawlowski., Nathan, J., Waddoups., David, A., Wood. (2021). A Framework for Using Robotic Process Automation for Audit Tasks. *Social Science Research Network*, <https://doi.org/10.2139/SSRN.3651028>
- Maria, do, Rosário, Cabrita., Francisca, Pargana., João, Costa. (2021). Robotic Process Automation implementation framework in a financial institution. <https://doi.org/10.23919/CISTI52073.2021.9476662>
- Oshri, I., & Plugge, A. (2021). Introducing RPA and automation in the financial sector: Lessons from KAS Bank. *Journal of Information Technology Teaching Cases*, 2043886921994828.
- Ramona, Lacurezeanu., Adriana, Tiron-Tudor., Vasile, Paul, Bresfelean. (2020). Robotic Process Automation in Audit and Accounting. <https://doi.org/10.20869/AUDITF/2020/160/024>
- Sara, Séguin., Hugo, Tremblay., Imène, Benkalai., David-Emmanuel, Perron-Chouinard., Xavier, Lebeuf. (2021). Minimizing the number of robots required for a Robotic Process Automation (RPA) problem. *Procedia Computer Science*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.PROCS.2021.09.039>
- Susan, Otaru., Umaru, Mustapha, Zubairu., Grace, Bikefe., Yakubu, Mustapha., Simeon, Araga., Afisat, Ayorinde. (2020). Robotic Process Automation and effectiveness of financial decisions: A critical review. <https://doi.org/10.22219/JIBE.V4I01.9621>
- Vijai, C., Suriyalakshmi, S. M., & Elayaraja, M. (2020). The Future of Robotic Process Automation (RPA) in the Banking Sector for Better Customer Experience. *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, 8(2), 61-65.
- Xun, Li. (2021). Research on the Application of Financial Robot under the Background of Next Generation Information Technology -- Taking Sinochem International as an example. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1827/1/012068>
- Yu, Lian, Qiu., Guo, Fang, Xiao. (2020). Research on Cost Management Optimization of Financial Sharing Center Based on RPA. *Procedia Computer Science*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.PROCS.2020.02.031>
<https://www.clariontech.com/platform-blog/8-unparalleled-benefits-of-rpa-that-will-power-up-your-business>
<https://www.klippa.com/en/blog/information/robotic-accounting/#:~:text=Robotic%20accounting%20is%20a%20form.in%20this%20case%2C%20accounting%20tasks.>
<https://www.kofax.com/learn/blog/12-innovative-use-cases-rpa-finance-accounting>
<https://egs.itc.com/blog/robotic-process-automation-in-accounting-and-finance-benefits-and-use-cases>
<https://francispress.com/papers/11069>
https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-89508-2_5
<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10151192>